

Remarks on the Difficulty of Encoding Feelings

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Abstract

The methodological crux of emotional design lies in the taxonomic variability arising from the complexity of the occasions at which we produce emotions.

Designers normally produce the forms in which things appear, sign systems or images, which, since it is necessary that these can be fitted into a variety of contexts, are therefore more or less abstract. Maybe design shifts from being a generalizing discipline to an individualizing discipline where, as with a bespoke tailor, work is done for small groups or for individual consumers.

A semiotization of the world means, alongside the reductionist visualization of practical life, looking through and beyond the things we see: behind the goods, we see a value; behind the products or spaces, we see functions; behind the letters, we see concepts, etc.

The three main rationalizing forces of development -- Euclidean space, money and semiotics -- also have their roots, though, in the social control of emotions.

A social fabric is also characterized by the fact that its members take pains to achieve justice in the interactive exchange of feelings. The relationships that thus come into being can be described as conventions, as stabilizing systems of mutual emotional expectations on the part of the partners involved.

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One of the central correlations on which the entire functioning of post-modern, consumer society is built, a society whose most important project is not survival but finding a sense in life through the having of experiences, consists in the link between what the consumer is aiming for in the way of experiences and what the supplier of goods and services promises him in the way of same. Experience-oriented aims are directed at the qualities of the experiencing, with the extent to which both these qualities are attractive and their potential to afford satisfaction being determined by emotions. Whether a new car provides that driving experience or not, whether a video-clip is exciting or boring, whether one's arrival at the station involves confusion, curiosity or pleasure, it is emotions which are aimed at, it is emotions with which situations, things or media representations are evaluated, and it is emotions which act as the touchstone in assessing whether the experience has indeed fulfilled its promise.

It is incumbent upon the supplier to set in motion those conditioning processes which establish the experiencing of certain emotions as the consequence of apprehending certain stimuli concomitant with his products, or, based on a conditioning that has already taken place, to design his products correspondingly. And here the lines which both the promises and the aims of experience take are many and various.

Even the processes of functional use in which artefacts are involved include an emotional element, a fact that becomes apparent as soon as the pull-tab on the can of beer fails to work. Producing positive emotions here, though, is easiest in that the product requires only to fulfill the function(s) expected of it properly.

It is more difficult, however, in those areas where happiness is promised. The scent of a soap, the style of driving a technically advanced automobile makes possible, the enjoyment of new and exotic international dishes, or even a feeling of omnipotence when working at the computer can convey the experience of belonging to happiness communities whether wholly subjectively or interpersonally with regard to the semiotic marking of groups and group norms. The links between material or media forms and concrete emotions are, however, not as straightforward as those regarding utilitarian functions.

The methodological crux of the process of Design lies in the taxonomic variability arising from the complexity of the occasions at which we produce emotions, that is, in the concrete nature of the scripts that it is intended to capture prototypically. That is why general emotional effects are best susceptible of description and prediction for literary texts or films and narrative image structures since these accurately convey complexities in the form sufficiently concrete for this.

It is more difficult here for designers; after all they normally produce the forms in which things appear, sign systems or images, which, since it is necessary that these can be fitted into a variety of contexts, are therefore more or less abstract. Consequently, the question as to the methods of planning the emotional effects of design can only be directed towards those typical, shared contexts consisting of frequently occurring situations involving applications or experiences. Or, however, design shifts from being a generalizing discipline to an individualizing discipline where, as with a bespoke tailor, work is done for small groups or for individual consumers. And with the increasing power of new technologies and media in

the way of diversification, this, too, is a possible route to follow, at the very latest when design is involved in the immediate technical control of complex qualities of perception, for example, through the use of Nano Technology.

The difficulties surrounding a generalizing comprehension of the interrelations of objects and emotions have, however, a dimension that has to do with cultural history and with the way in which the world is viewed, a dimension which in its dynamic makes even fundamental innovations seem conceivable.

So it is that one of the contradictions of modernism consists, on the one hand, in striving after the ideal types of things, in the sense outlined by Plato, in other words, in designing what is of the essence, the essential, and, on the other, through the adoption of an approach that would analyse by function, in largely removing human beings' emotional relationships to things from the determining nature of this essentiality, thus breaking entireness and thereby precisely the essentiality of things, in other words, comprehending "essentiality" exclusively in rationalist terms. A post-modern change requires neither the rejection of the concept of essentiality nor its revision.

The traditional occidental understanding of beingness and essentiality, notional concepts beneath the perceptible surface of the world, as it is set out in Plato's theory of ideas, or which also shines through in Zeno's conclusions in the famous *aporai* (e.g., Achilles' inability to overtake the tortoise), and which in any case is constitutive for the Christian picture of the world, hinders our emotional access to things in the respect that we name and make emotionality less conscious, and that we attempt normatively to substitute our being fundamentally emotionally motivated with rational grounds for our actions. In everyday life this basic disposition in the way the world is viewed is borne by three organizational principles for interpreting reality: Euclidean space, semiotics and the general transitivity of the world as expression of money.

This finds its correspondence in the inadequate awareness and impaired picture of the emotional effects the signs of things and images exert as well as in a general neglect of non-semiotic, non-transitive-abstract, non-hypothetically distant relationships to the world such as are assumed for pre-Renaissance societies or such as occur even today in extreme situations, for example, in states of intoxication, of panic or during certain multimedia demonstrations,

too. Here we have to do not so much with a neglect of emotions themselves, for as living beings we cannot but behave emotionally as well, but much rather with a culture of emotionality that lags behind rationality, with the suppression and internalization of feelings. A further aspect of the rational-functional and semiotic distance to our reality lies in the latter's untouchableness. If we just consider for a moment what we may touch, in other words, with just what we actually establish skin contact, we notice that it is mainly well-defined areas of our surroundings: clothing, knobs, keys, steering wheels, hands ..., interfaces that as such are prepared primarily for our hands. Through our clothing, contact mainly takes place with surfaces that are likewise suitably prepared: with seats, pedals, tables, level floors, etc. "... in buildings and cities' constructions we literally lose touch with physical reality." (Sennett, 1998, pp. 479-509; p. 488)

Just where and how things stand in relation to us is, in a tendency towards abstraction and in delimited sensuality, to a considerable extent strategically planned in terms of function. Much the same can be said about the concept of middle-class individuality. The distance to things corresponds to the distance maintained to one another by individuals of middle-class independent status. Things are each optimized to meet our respective demands. We move between them in great safety, hygienically and largely free of danger; and where hazards become recognizable, these are quickly eliminated. Yet our movements are the results of "elaborate ballets" (*ibid.*, p. 487), our body is a reproduction of images of the body discursively determined, our feelings follow conventions along relatively narrow paths, conventions that are predominantly rules governing the distances to be kept. Such cool relationships to our surroundings result in a turning inwards, that is, as a consequence of the limited possibilities available for tactile contact, we see and imagine tactile contacts, and, instead of following them through, we live inside of our selves as an internal network of yearnings and admonishments. A fear of touching preserves the distances, and emotionality as a whole is subject to the control over the delimits of expression.

Whereas a privatized subjectivity treats inner life as a transcendent, individual condition, and the contents of that inner life as a secret hidden from others -- and often also, if not a secret, at least a puzzle to the individual. ... This regime of subjectivity is just the danger of a society which eschews the embrace of resistance (*Ibid.*, p. 490).

The internalization of feelings is, on the one hand, a hindrance to the development of

reflexive emotion-related systems since inwardness remains individual, yet, on the other, it is serves as a relief insofar as expressions of feeling are conventionalized to a high degree of generality in those places where they occur. Sennett takes the connections further:

The mass-media protected fantasy offers a clue to understanding a larger cultural regime which regulates the sense of touch: withdrawal from physical contact occurs for the sake of stimulating inner life. The issue of inner-ness seems to me the crucial element of this regime of protected fantasy. Ghostly presences lurk in this withdrawal: these ghosts' presences are desire and longing. And these are subjective formations of a particular kind: longing for what is absent, desire for an ideal which cannot be consummated (*Ibid.*, p. 489).

Sennett's critique of society must be qualified at this point, for desires and longings, in both the productive and creative as well as the individual, identity-forming sense, are also decisive driving forces in human creativity.

And nor, of course, is the fantasy "protected" in an absolute sense from the mass media. The media set guidelines for the fantasy, and the closer they are in concrete terms, i.e., the more they correspond to our multi-sensual nature, the less room there remains, starting from a guideline, for imagining worlds of one's own. But, without the mass media, our fantasy as well as our emotionality have fewer occasions for development; the mass media differentiate the fantasy reflectively. And invariably where one person sets guidelines and another takes these over there lurks the danger of control, restriction, manipulation (one person follows another's instructions and thereby infringes his own independence, possibly acting against his own interests and, under certain circumstances, failing to recognize the position he is in). Whether, though, manipulation actually takes place is a very complicated question involving the social, economic and political situation in which the whole thing occurs. As we have seen, there exist, especially for design -- from product design to media design -- an extraordinarily large number of possible connections which can lead the fantasy in a virtually endless variety of directions. When Sennett formulates these relationships as a critique of power, he after all also leaves it open as to who exercises power over whom with what aims and in which connections. And much, though, depends on this.

Any withdrawal into inner life only takes place to the extent to which the contents of longings and desires are not communicated. Yet this is precisely what also happens with the mass

media. Especially as a result of the print media, radio and television -- here also because of the much-maligned talk shows and soaps -- and as a result of the Internet, we today basically know everything about how other people live and what experiences they have. The patterns in which ways of behaviour and viewpoints, values and attitudes are trained are essentially public, even if a not inconsiderable dynamic prevails here. It is precisely here, within this public realm, that the chance for designers lies. The methodical problem of targeting people's emotional reactions to products is not so much to be found in the privacy of everyday life. And the process of overcoming privacy is witnessing a new dimension with the advent of new virtual-reality media.

As instances of public subjectivity Sennett adduces the religious convictions of Christians, Moslems and Jews, as well as the so-called "moral sentiments" of such philosophers of the Enlightenment as Voltaire, Jefferson and Adam Smith (*Ibid.*, p. 490).

What young people in a discotheque today sense and feel is, in a way very similar to that in religious communities, general, communicable and in no way secret in any respect whatsoever.

A decisive condition for the predominance of the visual sense in our culture is to be found in the fact that visual media are technically highly developed, although this has been already significantly qualified through the telephone and the radio, as well through the audio components of film, television and the computer. And we shall witness a similar qualification when tactile experiences can be adequately transmitted technically and can be presented in their various nuances. The data-glove would appear to be a start in this direction. When this proximate sense becomes technically available in everyday life, so will people become more aware of the needs conveyed this way, and then it will be possible to cultivate this sense. A conceivable example of such is sensory appliances which, on being touched by a person, suitably react with changes to the surface, just as virtual orchestras are today already playing according to a person's arm movements, in other words, can be conducted by anybody. Expressions of feeling will thus be transposed in an interactive medium and, externalized, will be capable of being experienced. And at some time in the future we will be involved in a discussion about how restricted we feel tactilely, manipulated as we are by the technical guidelines.

Plato and Aristotle, the classical figures of occidental philosophy, attempted -- albeit in opposing directions -- to understand *aisthesis* in respect of its functions for *logos*. Sensory nature is reduced in the direction of the facial senses, ultimately to the "eye of the soul", and emotionality is to be found, so to speak, in the tow of sensory nature, as Sybille Krämer set out in an impressive lecture delivered in Bonn in 1997 (Krämer, 1998; pp. 24-39).

The privileged position accorded to the sense of sight over the other senses, the rationalization of seeing from a centralized perspective, the immaterialization of the space between straight walls, behind the cinema screen, the monitor, the printed page, sound waves ("It concerns the spirit, which is not the printed letter, it concerns the sense beyond the wording." (*Ibid.*, p. 27)) are manifestations of a general sensorial depletion and thus, too, of a de-emotionalization of an ever faster-moving middle-class world made up of functional routines.

A semiotization of the world means, alongside the reductionist visualization of practical life, looking through and beyond the things we see: behind the goods, we see a value; behind the products or spaces, we see functions; behind the letters, we see concepts, etc.

Though the problem is, in the first instance, a problem of perception, it is also a problem of the emotions. We feel differently when we look through and beyond things than we do when in our behaviour we put no distance between them and ourselves. But do we not in fact feel precisely because we look through things and create semantic levels, in greater numbers and more differentiated? And does not our act of feeling become more controllable and producible the further we distance ourselves from first-level reality?

A world of imagination made up of qualities of feeling that are available on demand can be a world that is really controlled by a really independent subject. In view of the existential dimensions of feelings, an independence of the subject that includes feelings should be an independence superior to that which only comprehends rationality.

We are living in a period in which the value of perception has already increased. Alone the broad extension of the concept of design testifies to this, and today the significance of images is on everybody's lips. If, for example, typography is playing an increasing role above and beyond pure ergonomics, i.e., beyond simply the ease of legibility of typefaces, then this is

evidence that the perception of the letters itself has become important again. The reasons for this lie in the pressure of demand for experiences, in the differentiation of the experiences offered, and in the difficulty entailed in attaining experience-oriented aims (experience-oriented aims are often harder to achieve than survival-oriented aims since the former are more difficult to pinpoint -- it is relatively easy to establish when a heated house protects against cold and from freezing to death (survival-oriented aims), but it is harder to decide when a house meets the demands of homeliness or prestige, etc. (experience-oriented aims). These reasons also result in our according greater value to our emotionality in our practical lives and in the way we view the world.

The three main rationalizing forces of development -- Euclidean space, money and semiotics -- also have their roots, though, in the social control of emotions. Heinz-Günter Vester draws our attention to the fact that important processes of exchange in society from its earliest beginnings to the present day are related not only to objects, territory, knowledge and services but also to emotions (Vester, 1991, pp. 111ff.).

A social fabric is also characterized by the fact that its members take pains to achieve justice in the interactive exchange of feelings. Strictly formulated, however, it does not concern a true exchange of feelings, but the comparison of emotionally based attitudes to one another; offers of emotional units of expression that provoke a suitable conventionalized reaction on the part of the other person in order to have them answered in precisely such a manner that an appropriate emotional reaction can be inferred. In fact it here involves genuine exchange relationships that are entered into with value assessments. Showing positive feelings like love, affection, respect, etc. demands from the partner an equivalent depending on social position: likewise love, affection, respect or protection, recognition, integration, money, material objects, etc. In short: expressions of feelings are exchanged for expressions of feelings, but equally for other things, which in turn have value apportioned them.

Even purely materially related acts of exchange and/or the exchange of goods normally have, in addition to an objective, functional aim, an emotional one, too. It can be assumed that, when goods are exchanged, even in advanced goods/money relationships, these emotional aims are nevertheless interwoven as mutual expectations, and this even when for the interacting partners it involves institutions that have been rendered more or less anonymous. People of one sort or another are always behind commercial transactions and need emotional

aims in order to trade.

The apportioning of value to exchangeable things is ultimately based in its quantity on the respective potential of these things for making an emotional profit, in other words, for being suitable for the attaining of experience-oriented aims, aims which essentially are emotionally determined: to what extent, for example, are certain culinary dishes suited to producing feelings of having eaten a sufficiency or, too, to producing good taste-experiences -- on the other hand: to what extent are the things exchanged for culinary dishes capable for their part of triggering positive feelings? For the act of exchange it remains important to what extent the things in the forms in which they appear induce references anticipatorily to what emotional patterns in the persons involved in this act -- a fundamental task facing design. In this sense aims of survival are also experience-oriented aims. [1]

The exchange of emotions is thus integrated into a complex system of exchange. The rationalization of acts of exchange via the employment of money is, in its measurability for the persons involved, also both a result of the striving for equilibrium ultimately in the mutual assignment of emotions and an expression of emotional balances. The emotional balancing is turned into a negotiable form via the monetary process:

A concern central to social relationships is the attainment of balanced reciprocity. According to this principle, it depends [however -- R.F.] not on a zero-zero bottom line between performance and counter-performance but on the appropriateness of the exchange, which also tolerates disadvantageous and preferential exchanges. The definition of 'appropriateness' is, though, a social and cultural problem (Vester, 1991, p. 114).

The establishment of the degree of reciprocity in an act of exchange is likewise performed emotionally: as annoyance at being personally disadvantaged, feelings of guilt and shame, or pride at one's own advantage, etc.

The decisive difference between simple acts of exchange and comparison with regard to emotions and goods/money transactions consists in the metered expression of value by means of money. Money makes possible the abstraction of the emotional balancing that is peculiar to developed economies.

The commensurability of values is based on a logical function, that of transitivity, of regarding two different elements as equal, based on the fact that both are equal to a third element: if $a = z$ and $b = z$, then it follows that $a = b$. Based on the universality of goods/money relationships in middle-class society, the principle of transitivity has become a universal model for interpreting reality, that is, we have grown accustomed to regarding things basically as being capable of being offset against each other, in relation to a third thing. Similar happens, too, through the other forms of semiotization of the world, putting distances between subject and object.

The functionalistic fragmentation and the semiotic differentiation of products are two aspects of this. They have, on the one hand, the effect that we experience things as the end-points of functional strings which are exchangeable with regard to their suitability for fulfilling functions and which are continually being substituted with regard to their suitability for optimizing functions through increasing differentiation. They also have, on the other hand, the effect that we likewise exchange artefacts with regard to their suitability for expressing meanings -- in very much the same way as we use various verbal languages -- and are continually substituting these artefacts with regard to their suitability for optimizing the expression of meanings through increasing differentiation -- something which occurs in verbal language, too, but spread over a much longer period of time. The distance that is thus maintained to things as qualitative units, as already shown above, relegates emotionality to the sphere of private individuality in order to communicate it from there -- again with the semiotic distance of the artefacts used for this. It is part of us and alien at the same time, but which also can be experienced in a differentiation that is unattainable without semiotic distance and as such suited to the aim of living the good life.

The relationships that thus come into being can be described as conventions, as stabilizing systems of mutual emotional expectations on the part of the partners involved: A shows his joy to B and expects B to share his joy. B sees A's expression of joy and expects that A expects him to share his joy. A expects from B that B expects from A that A expects B to share his joy, and so on. And all possible things, images and signs can be embedded here: A shows B his sofa and expects B to recognize that, through his showing it to B, he is expressing his pride about his possession, pride that is for his part is founded on the fact that A, through his possession of the sofa, counts himself as a member of the group of intellectual individualists because A has seen numerous people whom he considers to be intellectual

individualists with things shaped very much like his sofa, and assumes that B is conscious of this connection. Furthermore, A now expects B to be likewise proud of A because A and B are friends. B sees A's act of showing and expects that A expects him to share his feelings of pride, etc. Out of the large number of repetitions of similar situations, stabilities develop in the expectations each has of the other, stabilities which after a certain time are conventionized in rules, that is, which, depending on the number of people involved, are common to a kindred group. More general links are then established at various meta-levels between artefacts and emotional qualities.

[1] Schulze differentiates between the experience society, in which, with mass consumption as its basis, acts are predominantly experience-oriented, and earlier societies in which primarily aims of survival determined human activity. If hunger, thirst and sexual desire are counted among emotions, then it becomes clear that aims of survival are likewise essentially of emotional quality. Cp. G. Schulze. 1995. *Die Erlebnisgesellschaft*; 5th edition; Frankfurt/Main, New York

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